

The General First Zagreb Index, the Laplacian Spectral Radius and Some Hamiltonian Properties of Graphs

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Abstract

Let G be a graph. The general first Zagreb index of G is defined as the sum of the α th powers of the vertex degrees of G , where α is a real number such that $\alpha \neq 0$ and $\alpha \neq 1$. The Laplacian spectral radius of G is the largest eigenvalue of the Laplacian matrix of G . In this paper, we first prove an inequality on the general first Zagreb index with $\alpha > 1$ and the Laplacian spectral radius of a graph. Using that inequality, we present sufficient conditions involving the general first Zagreb index with $\alpha > 1$ and the Laplacian spectral radius for some Hamiltonian properties of a graph.

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1 Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notation and terminology not defined here follow those in [2]. Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with n vertices and e edges. The complement of G is denoted by G^c . We use $\delta = d_1 \leq d_2 \leq \dots \leq d_n = \Delta$ to denote the degree sequence of a graph G . For a subset S of the vertex set of G , we use $G[S]$ to denote the subgraph of G which is induced by S . A graph which does not have any edge is called an empty graph. For two graphs H_1 and H_2 , we define $H_1 \leq H_2$ as $V(H_1) = V(H_2)$ and $E(H_1) \subseteq E(H_2)$. The join of two disjoint graphs H_1 and H_2 is denoted by $H_1 \vee H_2$. A set of vertices in a graph G is independent if the vertices in the set are pairwise nonadjacent. A maximum independent set in a graph G is an independent set of the largest possible size. The independence number, denoted $\beta(G)$, of a graph G is the cardinality of a maximum independent set in G . For disjoint vertex subsets X and Y of $V(G)$, we use $E_G(X, Y)$ to denote the set of all the edges in $E(G)$ such that one end vertex of each edge is in X and another end vertex of the edge is in Y . Namely, $E_G(X, Y) := \{e : e = xy \in E, x \in X, y \in Y\}$. We use K_p to denote a complete graph of order p . We also use $K_{p,q}$ to denote a complete bipartite graph with two partition sets X and Y such that $|X| = p$ and $|Y| = q$. The Laplacian matrix of a graph G , denoted $L(G)$, is defined as $D(G) - A(G)$, where $D(G)$ is the diagonal matrix $\text{diag}(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n)$ of G and $A(G)$ is the adjacency matrix of G . We use $0 = \lambda_1(G) \leq \lambda_2(G) \leq \dots \leq \lambda_n(G)$ to denote the eigenvalues of $L(G)$. We call $\lambda_n(G)$ as the Laplacian spectral radius of G . A cycle C in a graph G is called a Hamilton cycle of G if C contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called Hamiltonian if G has a Hamilton cycle. A path P in a graph G is called a Hamilton path of G if P contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called traceable if G has a Hamilton path.

The first Zagreb index was introduced by Gutman, Rušćić, Trinajstić, and C. F. Wilcox in [6]. Also see [7]. For a graph G , its first Zagreb index is defined as $\sum_{v \in V(G)} d_G^2(v)$. Li and Zheng in [13] further extended the first Zagreb index of a graph and introduced the concept of the general first Zagreb index of a graph. The general first Zagreb index of a graph G , denoted $M_\alpha(G)$, is defined as $\sum_{v \in V(G)} d_G^\alpha(v)$, where α is a real number such that $\alpha \neq 0$ and $\alpha \neq 1$. Some results on the general first Zagreb index of a graph can be found in [1], [9], [10], [11], [12], and [13]. In this paper, we

first prove an inequality on the general first Zagreb index with $\alpha > 1$ and the Laplacian spectral radius of a graph. Using that inequality, we present sufficient conditions involving the general first Zagreb index with $\alpha > 1$ and the Laplacian spectral radius for Hamiltonian graphs and traceable graphs.

Using an inequality established by Chen and Qian in [3], Li [10] presented sufficient conditions based on the general first Zagreb index for Hamiltonian and traceable graphs. In this paper, we will continue to work along this direction. Particularly, we will use the same inequality in [3] and an existing result on the lower bound of the Laplacian spectral radius to obtain a new upper bound for the general first Zagreb index and new sufficient condition based on general first Zagreb index and the Laplacian spectral radius for Hamiltonian and traceable graphs. The main results of this paper are as follows.

Theorem 1. Let G be a graph with n vertices, e edges, and minimum degree $\delta \geq 1$. If $\alpha > 1$ is a real number, then

$$M_\alpha \leq \beta(n - \beta)^\alpha \left(\frac{\lambda_n}{n} \right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}} + (n - \beta)\Delta^\alpha$$

with equality if and only if $G \in \{ H : (G[I] \vee G[S]) \leq H \leq (G[I] \vee G[T]) \}$, where I is a maximum independent set of size β in G , $S = T = V - I$, $G[S]$ is an empty graph of order $(n - \beta)$, $G[T]$ is a complete graph of order $(n - \beta)$, and $d_H(v) = \Delta$ for each $v \in V - I$ }.

Theorem 2. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 2$) graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices and e edges. Assume $\alpha > 1$ is a real number. If

$$M_\alpha \geq (k + 1)(n - k - 1)^\alpha \left(\frac{\lambda_n}{n} \right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}} + (n - k - 1)\Delta^\alpha,$$

then G is Hamiltonian or $G \in \{ H : K_{k,k+1} \leq H \leq K_{k+1}^c \vee K_k \}$ and $d_H(v) = \Delta$ for each vertex v in H with $d_H(v) \neq \delta = k$ }.

Theorem 3. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 1$) with n vertices and e edges.

Assume $\alpha > 1$ is a real number. If

$$M_\alpha \geq (k+2)(n-k-2)^\alpha \left(\frac{\lambda_n}{n} \right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}} + (n-k-2)\Delta^\alpha,$$

then G is traceable or $G \in \{H : K_{k,k+2} \leq H \leq K_{k+2}^c \vee K_k \text{ and } d_H(v) = \Delta \text{ for each vertex } v \text{ in } H \text{ with } d_H(v) \neq \delta = k\}$.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we will give a list of existing results which will be used in our proofs of the three theorems above. In Section 3, we will present proofs of the three theorem above. Finally, we will present a summary of the research in this paper.

2 Lemmas

We will use the following results as our lemmas. Lemma 1 below is from the proof of Proposition 1 on Page 145 in [3].

Lemma 1 [3]. Let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_t be positive real numbers. Suppose p is a real number with $p > 1$. Then

$$\sum_{i=1}^t a_i^p \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^t a_i \right)^{\frac{p}{2p-1}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^t a_i^{2p} \right)^{\frac{p-1}{2p-1}}.$$

Lemma 2 below is from Proposition 2.1 on Page 173 in [14].

Lemma 2 [14]. Let G be a graph of order n . For any nontrivial subset X of vertices of G , $X \neq \emptyset$, $X \neq V(G)$, we have

$$\lambda_n \geq \frac{n|E(X, V-X)|}{|X||V-X|}.$$

Lemma 3 below is Lemma 13.1.3 on Page 280 in [5].

Lemma 3 [5]. If G is a graph on n vertices and $2 \leq i \leq n$, then $\lambda_i(G^c) = n - \lambda_{n-i+2}(G)$.

The next two lemmas are from [4].

Lemma 4 [4]. Let G be a k -connected graph of order $n \geq 3$. If $\beta \leq k$, then G is Hamiltonian.

Lemma 5 [4]. Let G be a k -connected graph of order n . If $\beta \leq k + 1$, then G is traceable.

3 Proofs

Proof of Theorem 1. We will use some ideas and techniques developed in [10] in our proofs. Let G be a graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices, e edges, and $\delta \geq 1$. Assume $\alpha > 0$ is a real number. Let $I := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_\beta\}$ be a maximum independent set in G . Set $V - I := \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n-\beta}\}$. Notice that $\delta \leq d(u_i) \leq n - \beta$ for each i with $1 \leq i \leq \beta$. Applying Lemma 1 with $t = \beta$, $p = \alpha$, and $a_i = d(u_i)$, where $1 \leq i \leq \beta$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^\alpha(u_i) &\leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d(u_i)\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^{2\alpha}(u_i)\right)^{\frac{\alpha-1}{2\alpha-1}} \\ &\leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d(u_i)\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}} (\beta(n-\beta)^{2\alpha})^{\frac{\alpha-1}{2\alpha-1}}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d(u_i)\right)^\alpha \geq \beta^{1-\alpha} (n-\beta)^{2\alpha(1-\alpha)} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^\alpha(u_i)\right)^{2\alpha-1}.$$

From Lemma 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_n^\alpha &\geq \left(\frac{n|E(I, V-I)|}{|I||V-I|}\right)^\alpha = \left(\frac{n(\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d(u_i))}{\beta(n-\beta)}\right)^\alpha \\ &\geq \frac{n^\alpha (\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^\alpha(u_i))^{2\alpha-1}}{\beta^{2\alpha-1} (n-\beta)^{\alpha(2\alpha-1)}}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^\alpha(u_i) \leq \beta(n-\beta)^\alpha \left(\frac{\lambda_n}{n}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}}.$$

Hence

$$M_\alpha = \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^\alpha(u_i) + \sum_{j=1}^{n-\beta} d^\alpha(v_j) \leq \beta(n - \beta)^\alpha \left(\frac{\lambda_n}{n}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}} + (n - \beta)\Delta^\alpha.$$

If

$$M_\alpha = \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^\alpha(u_i) + \sum_{j=1}^{n-\beta} d^\alpha(v_j) = \beta(n - \beta)^\alpha \left(\frac{\lambda_n}{n}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}} + (n - \beta)\Delta^\alpha.$$

we, in review of the proofs above, have that $d(u) = n - \beta$ for each $u \in I$ and $d(v) = \Delta$ for each $v \in V - I$. Notice that the number of edges in $G[V - I]$ can be any integer from 0 to $(n - |I|)(n - |I| - 1)/2$. We have that $G \in \{H : (G[I] \vee G[S]) \leq H \leq (G[I] \vee G[T])\}$, where I is a maximum independent set of size β in G , $S = T = V - I$, $G[S]$ is an empty graph of order $(n - \beta)$, $G[T]$ is a complete graph of order $(n - \beta)$, and $d_H(v) = \Delta$ for each $v \in V - I$ }.

If $G \in \{H : (G[I] \vee G[S]) \leq H \leq (G[I] \vee G[T])\}$, where I is a maximum independent set of size β in G , $S = T = V - I$, $G[S]$ is an empty graph of order $(n - \beta)$, $G[T]$ is a complete graph of order $(n - \beta)$, and $d_H(v) = \Delta$ for each $v \in V - I$ }, then $G^c = K_\beta \cup (G[V - I])^c$. Notice that there is no any edge between graph K_β and graph $(G[V - I])^c$ in G^c . We have that $\lambda_1(K_\beta) = \lambda_1(G[V - I])^c = 0$. Thus $\lambda_1(G^c) = \lambda_2(G^c) = 0$. By Lemma 3, we have $\lambda_n(G) = n$. It is obvious that

$$M_\alpha = \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^\alpha(u_i) + \sum_{j=1}^{n-\beta} d^\alpha(v_j) = \beta(n - \beta)^\alpha \left(\frac{\lambda_n}{n}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}} + (n - \beta)\Delta^\alpha.$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 2. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 2$) graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices and e edges. Assume $\alpha > 1$ is a real number. Suppose G is not Hamiltonian. Then Lemma 4 implies that $\beta \geq k + 1$. Also, we have that $n \geq 2\delta + 1 \geq 2k + 1$ otherwise $\delta \geq k \geq n/2$ and G is Hamiltonian. Let $I_1 := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_\beta\}$ be a maximum independent set in G . Then $I := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{k+1}\}$ is an independent set in G . Repeating the proof of Theorem

1, we have that

$$M_\alpha \leq (k + 1)(n - k - 1)^\alpha \left(\frac{\lambda_n}{n}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}} + (n - k - 1)\Delta^\alpha.$$

From the conditions of Theorem 2, we have that

$$M_\alpha = (k + 1)(n - k - 1)^\alpha \left(\frac{\lambda_n}{n}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}} + (n - k - 1)\Delta^\alpha.$$

Following the proof of Theorem 1 again, we have $G \in \{H : (G[I] \vee G[S]) \leq H \leq (G[I] \vee G[T])\}$, where I is an independent set of size $k + 1$ in G , $S = T = V - I$, $G[S]$ is an empty graph of order $(n - k - 1)$, $G[T]$ is a complete graph of order $(n - k - 1)$, and $d_H(v) = \Delta$ for each $v \in V - I$.

If $(k + 1) \leq (n - k - 1)$, then $\frac{n}{2} = \frac{(k+1)+(n-k-1)}{2} \leq (n - k - 1) = d(u)$, where u is any vertex in I . Since $d(v) = \Delta$ for each $v \in V - I$, we have that $\delta \geq \frac{n}{2}$ and G is Hamiltonian, a contradiction.

Now we assume that $k \geq (n - k - 1)$. Thus $n \leq 2k + 1$. Therefore $n = 2k + 1$ and $G \in \{H : K_{k,k+1} \leq H \leq K_{k+1}^c \vee K_k$ and $d_H(v) = \Delta$ for each vertex v in H with $d_H(v) \neq \delta = k\}$.

This completes the proof of Theorem 2.

Proof of Theorem 3. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 1$) with n vertices and e edges. Assume $\alpha > 1$ is a real number. If $n = 1$ or $n = 2$, it is obvious that G is traceable. From now on we assume $n \geq 3$. Suppose G is not traceable. Then Lemma 5 implies that $\beta \geq k + 2$. Also, we have that $n \geq 2\delta + 2 \geq 2k + 2$ otherwise $\delta \geq k \geq (n - 1)/2$ and G is traceable. Let $I_1 := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_\beta\}$ be a maximum independent set in G . Then $I := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{k+2}\}$ is an independent set in G . Repeating the proof of Theorem 1, we have that

$$M_\alpha \leq (k + 2)(n - k - 2)^\alpha \left(\frac{\lambda_n}{n}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}} + (n - k - 2)\Delta^\alpha.$$

From the conditions of Theorem 2, we have that

$$M_\alpha = (k + 2)(n - k - 2)^\alpha \left(\frac{\lambda_n}{n}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2\alpha-1}} + (n - k - 2)\Delta^\alpha.$$

Following the proof of Theorem 1 again, we have $G \in \{H : (G[I] \vee G[S]) \leq H \leq (G[I] \vee G[T])\}$, where I is an independent set of size $k + 2$ in G , $S = T = V - I$, $G[S]$ is an empty graph of order $(n - k - 2)$, $G[T]$ is a complete graph of order $(n - k - 2)$, and $d_H(v) = \Delta$ for each $v \in V - I$.

If $(k + 1) \leq (n - k - 2)$, then $\frac{n-1}{2} = \frac{(k+1)+(n-k-2)}{2} \leq (n - k - 2) = d(u)$, where u is any vertex in I . Since $d(v) = \Delta$ for each $v \in V - I$, we have that $\delta \geq \frac{n-1}{2}$ and G is traceable, a contradiction.

Now we assume that $k \geq (n - k - 2)$. Thus $n \leq 2k + 2$. Therefore $n = 2k + 2$ and $G \in \{H : K_{k,k+2} \leq H \leq K_{k+2}^c \vee K_k \text{ and } d_H(v) = \Delta \text{ for each vertex } v \text{ in } H \text{ with } d_H(v) \neq \delta = k\}$.

This completes the proof of Theorem 3.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, we first establish an upper bound for the general first Zagreb index that involves the independence number, the Laplacian spectral radius, and the maximum degree of a graph. We also characterize the extremal graphs achieving the upper bound. In addition, using the ideas of obtaining the upper bound and the well-known Chvátal-Erdős conditions for Hamiltonian and traceable graphs, we present new sufficient conditions for Hamiltonian and traceable graphs. We also characterize extremal graphs satisfying the new conditions.

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